

Tailoring Portfolio, Program, and Project Management to a Complex System

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Abstract

Managing a complex portfolio of projects requires a mature structure that considers portfolio, program, and project management standards and best practices tailored to the specific system. This paper provides a framework for the development and implementation of a management model for a complex portfolio – the Erasmus+ initiative called *Egalitarian*. The research has an applied nature and utilizes an action research strategy with a qualitative approach. Based on a bibliographic review and observation, the paper analyses the portfolio management structure of the *Global Students SDG Challenge* and tailors a framework for an updated management model.

Keywords: Portfolio Management; Program Management; Project Management; Complex System; Tailoring; Framework.

1 Introduction

To prepare an engineering student for the job market, universities must develop not only technical skills but also transversal skills such as teamwork, leadership, communication, adaptability, and project management (Monteiro *et al.*, 2012). Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and Project-Based Learning (PjBL) are a good way for students to work in interdisciplinary teams and on real-world problems, achieving the competencies mentioned above (Pedersen *et al.*, 2020).

Initiatives that promote international and interdisciplinary student projects bring another level of cooperation, insights, and complexity, requiring a careful project design to ensure that the students can collaborate and yet fulfill the requirements and learning objectives of their home universities (Pedersen *et al.*, 2020). The *Global Students SDG Challenge* and now *Egalitarian* are two of these initiatives. *Egalitarian* is an Erasmus+ initiative co-funded by the European Union, and it has more than 25 teams working on approximately 8 programs each semester, involving students from Brazilian and European universities. Managing such a complex portfolio of projects requires a mature structure that considers portfolio, program, and project management standards and best practices.

This article's main objective is to provide a guide for the development and implementation of a management model for a complex portfolio. Its specific objectives are (i) to understand the current portfolio, program, and project management standards and best practices, (ii) to describe the model used for managing the *Global Students SDG Challenge* portfolio, and (iii) to propose a tailored framework for developing a new management model for the *Egalitarian* portfolio.

The paper is organized as follows. First, a theoretical background is presented, to give context and relevant information about the current best practices. After this, the research methodology is explained, followed by the results achieved from past research and a discussion based on the authors' experience with the *Global Students SDG Challenge* portfolio, and at last the conclusion.

2 Theoretical Background

This section introduces theoretical concepts that underpin the research.

2.1 Portfolio, Program, and Project Management

A portfolio consists of a collection of projects, programs, subsidiary portfolios, and related operations managed in an integrated way to achieve an organization's strategic objectives. A program includes related projects, subsidiary programs, and program activities managed in a coordinated manner to obtain benefits not available from managing them individually. Programs and individual projects with strategic importance are part of a portfolio – even if they are not directly related or interdependent – if they are linked to the organization's strategic plan through the portfolio. (PMI, 2017a)

Portfolio management focuses on ensuring the portfolio is performing consistently with the organization's objectives and evaluating portfolio components to optimize resource allocation, and program management applies knowledge, skills, and principles to a program to achieve the program objectives and obtain benefits and control not available by managing related program components individually (PMI, 2023). Project management is the application of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques to project activities to meet project requirements and deliver the intended outcomes (PMI, 2021).

Portfolio, program, and project management are based on principles and performance domains, such as: Obtain and maintain the sponsorship and engagement of senior management and key stakeholders; Navigate complexity to enable successful outcomes; Create a collaborative project team environment; Tailor based on context. (PMI, 2017a; 2021)

A major reason for project failure is the lack of benefits management (Walenta, 2016). Benefits management is not a knowledge area covered by project management, but by program management (PMI, 2017b). Large organizations and organizations that want to achieve higher levels of project management maturity need to separate program and project management, since project management standards focus on the traditional triangle of scope/quality, time, and cost, while the triangle for program management could be defined as strategy/benefits, governance, and stakeholders (Walenta, 2016).

Project management is also important in education contexts. Fernandes, Dinis-Carvalho and Ferreira-Oliveira (2021) studied the application of Scrum to complex Project-Based Learning environments and found that task assignment, performance monitoring, visual management, and regular feedback were considered the main advantages of using Scrum in PjBL teams, which had a positive impact on student performance.

2.2 Portfolio, Program, and Project Management Offices (PMOs)

An important role in portfolio, program, and project management is the PMO. At the portfolio level, a PMO is an organizational entity that provides various capabilities and processes supporting portfolio management (PMI, 2017a). A program management office standardizes the program-related governance processes and facilitates the sharing of resources, methodologies, tools, and techniques. It may be specific to an individual program, or support multiple organization's programs (PMI, 2017b). A project management office has a similar function to the program management office but at the project level. The projects supported or administered by the project management office may not be related other than by being managed together (PMI, 2023). The main activities and responsibilities for each type of PMO – Portfolio, Program, and Project Management Offices – can be found at Project Management Institute (2017a; 2017b; 2023).

The specific form, function, and structure of a PMO are dependent upon the needs of the organization that it supports. There are three main types of PMOs in organizations, varying the degree of control and influence it has on projects within the organization (PMI, 2023):

- **Supportive:** Supportive PMOs provide a consultative role to projects by supplying templates, best practices, training, access to information, and lessons learned from other projects. This type of PMO serves as a project repository. The degree of control provided by the PMO is low.
- **Controlling:** Controlling PMOs provide support and require compliance through various means. The degree of control provided by the PMO is moderate. Compliance may involve:
 - Adoption of project management frameworks or methodologies;
 - Use of specific templates, forms, and tools; and
 - Conformance to governance frameworks.
- **Directive:** Directive PMOs take control of the projects by directly managing the projects. Project managers are assigned by and report to the PMO. The degree of control provided by the PMO is high.

In the academic research environment, a PMO may also be useful. Widforss and Rosqvist (2015) analyze the PMO of a Swedish university, which provides professional project management services to researchers and research projects. The survey conducted shows that structure, tools, and templates are less useful for complex projects than governance, management support, experience, and skill. Fernandes, Souza, Tereso and O'Sullivan (2021) present three PMO structures for University Research Centres (URCs) with a total of twenty-six functions. These are divided into the three PMO typologies, with an evolution logic: 'basic' PMO, 'intermediate' PMO, and 'advanced' PMO. Functions go from general guidelines and definitions to strategic influence and direct management of the R&D projects.

2.3 Complex Systems and Systems Thinking

The inherent complexity of portfolio management often results in a context characterized by overlapping and potentially conflicting stakeholder interests. This complex landscape presents portfolio managers with the challenge of effectively navigating a high flow of unfiltered information while simultaneously experiencing not enough relevant communication (PMI, 2017a). Other components that influence portfolio and project complexity include, but are not limited to: number of unpredictable stakeholders who need individual care; dimension of change imposed on the environment; complicatedness or unpredictability of project results; timeline and number of parallel activities; organizational structure; geographic distribution (*Svenskt projektforum*, 2011, as cited in Widforss & Rosqvist, 2015).

A systems thinking approach tends to help analyze the portfolio system as a whole (PMI, 2017a), and understand how the portfolio system and subsystems fit into the larger context of the organization and day-to-day life (International Council on Systems Engineering, 2006).

The portfolio may be analyzed and managed as a System-of-Systems, i.e., as "an interoperating collection of component systems that produce results unachievable by the individual systems alone" (International Council on Systems Engineering, 2006), which helps portfolio managers to analyze the whole portfolio and focus on the effects of the interactions between the portfolio components. Employing a systems perspective facilitates a more comprehensive understanding of both the objectives driving change initiatives and the mechanisms employed to achieve them. This approach also provides valuable insights into the individual components of the portfolio and their interactions within the broader organizational system (PMI, 2017a).

2.4 Tailoring

Project Management Institute (2021) defines tailoring as "the deliberate adaptation of the project management approach, governance, and processes to make them more suitable for the given environment and the work at hand". Project aspects that can be tailored include life cycle and development approach selection, processes, engagement, tools, and methods and artifacts. The process of tailoring for the organization and for a specific project is composed of four steps (PMI, 2021):

- **Select Initial Development Approach:** Choose a development approach best suited for the endeavor;

- **Tailor for Organization:** Modify based on organizational modifications;
- **Tailor for Project:** Adjust based on size, criticality, and other factors;
- **Implement Ongoing Improvement:** Inspect and adapt.

According to Project Management Institute (2023), “tailoring is necessary because each project is unique”. The standards for portfolio, program, and project management identify several processes, tools, techniques, inputs, and outputs, but not everything is required for every project or group of projects. The importance of each constraint and performance domain is different for each project, program, or portfolio, and the management of these elements should be tailored based on the environment, organizational culture, stakeholder needs, and other variables (PMI, 2023).

Additional guidelines for tailoring, based on the Agile Practice Guide (PMI, 2017c), include: Restructure large projects as multiple smaller projects; Break large teams into multiple smaller teams and use program management to synchronize and coordinate; Use agile and lean program management to organize the larger effort; Use tools like instant messaging, video conferencing, and electronic team boards to help bridge communication gaps; Consider building centers of competencies to help provide guidance and build domain knowledge, especially when team members are inexperienced.

3 Methodology

This research has an applied nature and utilizes an action research strategy with a qualitative approach. A highly interactive method, action research is often used in educational settings, and it aims to simultaneously investigate and solve an issue (George, 2023). One of the characteristics of this method is the active role of the researcher as a true agent of intervention and change in organizations (Westbrook, 1995, as cited in Ganga, 2011).

This research has two steps. Step 1 focuses on presenting the portfolio, program, and project management model used by the production engineering undergraduate program at the University of Brasília. It complements the works made by Barreto (2022) and Brito (2023), and it uses both bibliographic analysis and observation techniques. Step 2 aims to suggest a framework for developing a new model for the portfolio, program, and project management of the international Erasmus+ program called *Egalitarian*. The framework consists of a tailoring of the portfolio, program and project management approach, governance, and processes. A literature review provided theoretical background for both steps.

4 Results and Discussions

4.1 Old Model

The production engineering course at the University of Brasília has a set of subjects with the proposal to apply the active learning methodology through projects that have scopes related to other technical subjects in the student's curriculum (Barreto, 2022). Some of these project-based subjects are integrated and were part of a portfolio of projects arising from the *Global Students SDG Challenge*, a student-centered initiative that connects students from different universities and countries to develop solutions that help achieve the 2030 Agenda's goals.

The portfolio involved courses and subjects from the University of Brasília, Brazil, and Aalborg University, Denmark. The PSP2 and PSP5 subjects were fixed subjects in the portfolio, and other subjects were involved depending on the projects being developed in a specific semester.

The Portfolio Board was made up of key professors and students that coordinated the PMO. Their main responsibility was to define the portfolio components, according to the *Global Students SDG Challenge* strategy and objectives. The PMO served many functions, such as (Brito, 2023):

- Strategic management and transformation, team and human resources management, and portfolio management, performed by professors in the Management role;
- Strategic management and guidance regarding the PMO, team and human resources management, and learning and knowledge management, performed by students in the Coordination role;
- Projects and programs monitoring, performed by students in the Control role; and
- Management of information tools and systems, management of data intelligence and communication, and management of processes and improvements, performed by students in the Support role.

Teams were integrated in a matrix way: students of the same subject interact and share lessons learned, and students of the same theme cooperate and work together to deliver their scopes. Same-subject interaction is encouraged by the subject professors, and same-theme synergy is influenced by the Control team of the PMO.

Projects inside the *Global Students SDG Challenge* portfolio used a hybrid project management approach that combined iteration-based agile approaches with predictive life cycle elements (PMI, 2017c). The project execution was divided into sprints, and the project deliverables were organized in backlogs with epics, user stories, and tasks. All tasks must have a Definition of Done (i.e., an acceptance criteria).

The PMO provided for each team the project context, general scope, and main deliveries from last semesters. At the beginning of the project executions, all teams should provide a filled Project Model Canvas (Finocchio Júnior, 2013) and an initial product backlog, based on the directions provided. For each sprint, the team must detail a sprint backlog and provide a status report for the PMO. These artifacts and information feed a dashboard from the PMO, used for monitoring the portfolio.

This model, that was used to manage the *Global Students SDG Challenge* portfolio, was updated each semester, based on lessons learned, results achieved, the portfolio's strategic objectives, and portfolio, program, and project management best practices. For the next three years, the *Global Students SDG Challenge* was replaced by *Egalitarian*, an Erasmus+ program that will involve not only the University of Brasília (Brazil) and Aalborg University (Denmark) but also the University of Minho (Portugal) and Saxion University (Netherlands). Therefore, the portfolio became more complex – with more stakeholders, professors, teams, and projects –, which requires a more robust management and control system, e. g., with key performance indicators being monitored (at a project and a portfolio levels). The framework proposed on the next topic aims to guide the development of a new model for the portfolio, program, and project management of the *Egalitarian* portfolio.

4.2 Proposed Framework

Based on (i) the portfolio, program and project management principles, performance domains, processes, tools, methods, and artifacts, (ii) the model used for managing the *Global Students SDG Challenge* portfolio, and (iii) the processes and guidelines for tailoring, this section details the proposed framework for managing the new *Egalitarian* portfolio. The framework focuses on the adjustments needed in the old model; elements presented in the last topic that aren't updated or altered in this topic remain under use.

Figure 1 shows the new portfolio structure. The subsidiary portfolios, one for each country/university, are composed of programs and projects that may be integrated into other programs and projects inside the other subsidiary portfolios. Teams from different universities should work together to deliver their projects in an integrated way, and the PMOs are responsible for facilitating that cooperation. The number and scope of programs and projects can vary for each semester.

Figure 1. New Portfolio Structure

Figure 2 shows the new portfolio management structure. The Portfolio Board members are the professors in the Management role inside the PMOs and the students in the Coordination role of the Main PMO. Other students and professors may be involved in the Portfolio Board if needed. Each PMO – here considered a Portfolio, Program, and Project Management Office – is responsible for managing a subsidiary portfolio. The Main PMO manages both its subsidiary portfolio and the Auxiliary PMOs. Each Team is responsible for executing a project, and it may have one of the two following structures: a Product Owner (PO), a Scrum Master (SM), and an Executing Team; or a Project Manager (PM) and an Executing Team. The structure adopted will depend on the Team's subject and university.

Figure 2. New Portfolio Management Structure. (¹adapted from Brito, 2023)

The Portfolio Board functions and responsibilities are: Define the portfolio strategy, objectives, and guidelines; Define the portfolio components and general project themes for each semester; Establish partnership guidelines; Develop the portfolio charter; Develop the portfolio roadmap; Manage the portfolio value. (adapted from Barreto, 2022 and PMI, 2017a)

Table 1 describes the Main PMO functions and responsibilities. Table 2 details the Auxiliary PMOs functions and responsibilities.

Table 1. Main PMO Functions and Responsibilities.

Role	Functions and Responsibilities
Management	<p>Strategic management and transformation: Manage resource allocation within the PMOs and the portfolio; Assist in the implementation of frameworks and methodologies for managing the portfolio, PMOs, subsidiary portfolios, and programs; Implement organizational changes and transformations in the PMOs.</p> <p>Team and human resources management: Define the expected profile of students for each PMO role; Select the PMO team.</p> <p>Portfolio management: Manage the portfolio; Monitor the portfolio performance.</p>
Coordination	<p>Strategic management and guidance regarding the PMOs: Guide resource allocation within the PMOs; Provide frameworks and methodologies for managing the portfolio, PMOs, subsidiary portfolios, and programs; Guide the need to implement organizational changes and transformations in the PMOs; Coordinate communication across portfolio components.</p> <p>Team and human resources management: Guide the expected profile of students for each PMO role; Execute the integration process for new PMO members; Develop and conduct training and mentoring of human resources in portfolio and program management skills, tools, and techniques; Monitor and advise Support and Control teams and Auxiliary PMOs.</p> <p>Learning and knowledge management: Manage the PMOs lessons learned meetings; Manage PMOs knowledge base; Train PMOs members.</p>
Control	<p>Portfolio and program monitoring: Monitor the subsidiary portfolio performance; Monitor the programs and subsidiary programs performance; Conduct project audit; Manage interfaces with project customers and project sponsors; Monitor projects and programs risks; Ensure the production of project reports by the Teams.</p>
Support	<p>Management of information tools and systems: Provide tools and information systems for project management, PMOs knowledge management, and portfolio metrics and KPIs management; Manage project documentation database; Provide training and support on the use of tools for PMOs members.</p> <p>Management of data intelligence and communication: Prepare periodic reports containing relevant insights into data acquired through tools and information systems used for project management.</p> <p>Management of processes and improvements: Carry out fault diagnosis in internal processes and identify improvement needs within the PMOs.</p>

(adapted from Barreto, 2022, Brito, 2023 and PMI, 2017a)

Teams functions and responsibilities may have two structures. In the first one, a Project Manager (PM) is responsible for managing project stakeholders, improving problem definition and project scope, providing project reports to the PMO, and managing project risks, while the Execution Team proactively study and seek possible solutions for the project, organize the deliveries for each milestone of the project timeline, and execute the project. In the second model, a Scrum Master (SM) lead, train, and guide the Team in adopting Scrum, help project members and stakeholders understand and apply an empirical approach to complex work, and remove barriers between stakeholders and the Team; a Product Owner (PO) develop and explicitly communicate the Product Goal, create and communicate Product Backlog items, prioritize Product Backlog items, and ensure the Product Backlog is transparent, visible, and understandable; and the Execution Team create a plan for the sprint – the Sprint Backlog –, gradually introduce quality by adhering to a Definition of Done, adapt the plan each day toward the Sprint Goal, and provide a status report for each sprint. (adapted from Barreto, 2022 and Schwaber & Sutherland, 2020)

Table 2. Auxiliary PMOs Functions and Responsibilities.

Role	Functions and Responsibilities
Management	<p>Strategic management and transformation: Manage resource allocation within the Auxiliary PMO and the subsidiary portfolio; Assist in the implementation of frameworks and methodologies for managing the Auxiliary PMO, subsidiary portfolios, and subsidiary programs; Implement organizational changes and transformations in the Auxiliary PMO.</p> <p>Team and human resources management: Select the Auxiliary PMO team.</p> <p>Subsidiary portfolio management: Manage the subsidiary portfolio; Monitor the subsidiary portfolio performance.</p>
Control	<p>Subsidiary portfolio and subsidiary program monitoring: Monitor the subsidiary portfolio performance; Monitor the subsidiary programs performance; Conduct project audit; Manage interfaces with project customers and project sponsors; Monitor projects and subsidiary programs risks; Ensure the production of project reports by the Teams.</p>

(adapted from Barreto, 2022, Brito, 2023 and PMI, 2017a)

The Main PMO serves as a Center of Excellence for the Auxiliary PMOs and the whole portfolio (PMI, 2017a). The number of professors and students in each role will depend on the capacity and capability analysis of each university, but ideally, a student in the Control role should be responsible for managing no more than 2 programs or subsidiary programs. On a project management level, the PMOs (specifically, the Control role) provide integration between teams, project scope, project management methodology, insights and mentoring, and project evaluation and feedback; the Teams provide status report, executive summary, difficulties and blockings, project deliveries, and ideas and feedback.

A framework is “a loose but incomplete structure which leaves room for other practices and tools to be included but provides much of the process required” (Think Insights, 2020). Therefore, the framework proposed in this section should serve as a guideline for the development of a new model for the portfolio, program, and project management of the *Egalitarian* portfolio. Additional tailoring may be necessary during the new model creation/implementation. Also, members from all 4 universities should be included in the next steps, to make sure that the final model fits all necessities and realities.

5 Conclusion

This paper contributes to the portfolio, program, and project management of an international Erasmus+ initiative that connects students and promotes interdisciplinary student projects, which impacts the students’ personal and professional development. It provides a guide for the development and implementation of a management model for a complex portfolio by analyzing the current standards and best practices and the model used for managing the *Global Students SDG Challenge* portfolio. The tailored framework proposed provides a new portfolio structure with defined roles and responsibilities.

Future research may explore similar frameworks for different systems and organizations or focus on the creation and implementation of the complete *Egalitarian* portfolio management model based on the proposed framework. A further analysis of the framework impact on teaching and learning, from both the professors and the students’ perspectives, is also welcomed.

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